

Compendium of Natural Epsilon-Near-Zero Materials

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Abstract: Epsilon-Near-Zero (ENZ) materials are among the most intriguing electromagnetic materials, enabling realization of electromagnetic field squeezing, wave steering, perfect absorption and ultrafast optical switching. These phenomena arise from the strong interactions of light with substances with a near-zero real part of the permittivity and provide a new realm for fabricating new optical and optoelectronic devices. However, ENZ materials are usually strongly dispersive and their unique properties manifest only near certain optical wavelengths. Therefore, designing devices with targeted performance and operational wavelength requires knowledge of the optical properties of a broad range of ENZ materials. Here we present a comprehensive dataset of natural materials, including metals, semiconductors, oxides, halides and others, which exhibit intrinsic dielectric permittivity around zero. The data highlight the wavelength ranges over which the ENZ behaviour occurs. Furthermore, we discuss application-specific quality factors and identify the most promising candidates for various applications across different spectral regions.

Keywords

Metamaterials, Epsilon-Near-Zero Materials, Plasmonics, Natural Materials, Electromagnetic Wave Engineering

Introduction

Epsilon-near-zero (ENZ) materials offer a highly attractive optical platform with nontrivial properties¹⁻³. Such materials are characterized by a real part of the dielectric permittivity, $\text{Re } \epsilon$, approaching zero within a specific frequency range. This gives rise to a number of intriguing phenomena, including: sub-wavelength confinement of electromagnetic fields, leading to enhanced optical nonlinearities⁴; supercoupling between two waveguides through narrow channels¹, facilitating the design of ultrahigh-speed information processing in integrated photonic

devices⁵ and perfect absorption for light harvesting applications⁶. Various applications of ENZ materials have been realized including: efficient antennas for microwave range wireless communication⁷; perfect absorbers; high-quality-factor sensing in the microwave range⁸; and THz wave generation⁹. Significant progress has also been made in the development of artificial ENZ materials (metamaterials and photonic crystals)^{10–16}, which can be useful in many platforms such as photonic chips and waveguides in zero-index photonics.

In this work, we provide a compendium of *natural* ENZ materials for the study and fabrication of ENZ structures. Previously, we have reported a similar compendium for natural hyperbolic materials¹⁷. Engineered structures, superlattices¹⁸, multilayers¹⁹, quantum dots with plasmonic shells²⁰, all-dielectric structured materials²¹, and ENZ organic compounds²² are excluded from our considerations. In order to quantify the efficiency of ENZ materials for different applications, we calculated a set of quality factors. Additionally, both real and imaginary part of the ENZ materials are provided, enabling the calculation of any quality factor based on specific applications.

The vanishing permittivity is typically accompanied by a change of its sign. Such behaviour occurs near certain resonance frequencies like plasmon, phonon, exciton²³, and magnon resonances²⁴, inter-band transitions, and cooper pair polaritons²⁵. The permittivity of a material with free carriers and far from the inter-band transitions is described by the Drude model expression²⁶:

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\infty} - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^2 - i\gamma\omega}, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{∞} is the background (high-frequency) permittivity, ω_p is the plasmonic frequency, and γ is the damping factor. Equation (1) determines the wavelengths at which materials exhibit ENZ behaviour. Noble metals and highly doped semiconductors are the most well-known materials showing ENZ properties in the visible and NIR spectral ranges. Additionally, transparent conductive oxides, such as ZnO, SnO doped with In, Al, or Ga, have been introduced as promising ENZ materials, less absorbing compared to the metals. Recently, a new group of emerging photonic materials – metal nitrides – have attracted great attention in plasmonics because of their high tunability, CMOS compatibility, and low loss in the IR range²⁷.

Another mechanism determining the permittivity is lattice vibrations, generally around phonon energies at the mid-IR range. In this case, the permittivity is described by the Lorentz formula

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{\omega_{LO}^2 - \omega_{TO}^2}{\omega_{TO}^2 - \omega^2 - i\Gamma\omega} \right), \quad (2)$$

where ω_{TO} and ω_{LO} are the transverse and longitudinal phonon frequencies; ϵ_{∞} is the high-frequency permittivity; and Γ is the damping constant²⁸. The ENZ regime for equation (2) occurs at longitudinal phonon frequencies and within the *Reststrahlen* band where the permittivity becomes negative. For example, the Reststrahlen range for a polar crystal, such as SiC is 10-12 μm ²⁹. The advantage of the phonon resonances over plasmon resonances is the low damping rates, leading to low losses. However, their main disadvantage is the low efficiency at the field enhancement, because the major portion of the energy is stored in lattice vibrations instead of electromagnetic waves³⁰. In addition, the use of phononic materials for ENZ applications is constrained by a limited wavelength operation range. Nevertheless, hybridization of ENZ modes with plasmon resonances offers a strategy to expand the functioning wavelength beyond the *Reststrahlen* band. For instance, the low level of electron doping in GaAs, leading to coupling between plasmon resonance and phonon vibrations, provides a tuneable wavelength range to support propagation of surface plasmon polaritons and ENZ modes²⁹.

In semiconductors, excitons (i.e, bound electron-hole pairs) determine the behaviour of permittivity around their binding energy and can be expressed as:

$$\epsilon_s = \epsilon_{\infty} + A \frac{\gamma}{\omega_0 - \omega - i\gamma}, \quad (3)$$

where A is a factor proportional to the exciton oscillator strength; γ is the damping factor; ϵ_{∞} is the high-frequency permittivity; and ω_0 is the inter-band transition frequency²³. The binding energy of excitons plays a crucial role in determining their lifetime and stability. When the binding energy is low, the thermal energy can unbind the electron-hole pairs. This affects the energy range in which exciton-polariton coupling sustains, typically in the visible and near-infrared (NIR) spectrum. For example, MoSe₂ exhibits long-propagating polariton modes, extending up to 12 μm at 800nm under ambient conditions³¹. This facilitates size reduction down to a few atomic layers, making it suitable for applications in nanophotonic circuits³² and design of unique anisotropic waveguides³¹.

The interaction between magnetic excitations and photons can also modify dielectric permittivity around the coupling resonance frequency, opening up the possibility of creating materials where the ENZ properties are driven by magnetic effects³³.

In addition to the above-mentioned resonances, the inter-band transitions have a dominant effect on permittivity around the transition frequency. For example, for Bi, Sb and Ga the inter-band transition changes the permittivity in the ultraviolet and visible spectral ranges, where free carriers

usually play the main role in permittivity constants³⁴. The inter-band transitions make negative contributions to the permittivity value, thereby providing conditions for near-zero permittivity. In this regard, the key parameters in the inter-band transition rates (e.g., the curvature of the energy bands and the band gap energy) determine the plasmonic properties and ENZ ranges. Thus, by engineering the electron energy bands one can tailor optical properties of materials.

In summary, the ENZ wavelengths of materials are determined by the type of resonance. Metals exhibit ENZ behaviour in the UV, visible and Near-IR ranges; whereas polar dielectrics, such as hBN, GaAs and InP, achieve the ENZ regime in the MIR range.

To sort ENZ materials in terms of the efficiency, we have used similar ideas in the plasmonic field to define proper quality factors. A survey on quality factors for plasmonic materials has been conducted by Tassin *et al.*³⁵, showing that a trade-off between different factors is essential to select proper materials for specific applications. The quality factor of a plasmonic material in the quasistatic approximation and lossless regime at a near-resonant frequencies can be expressed as³⁶:

$$Q_{pl} = \frac{\omega}{2\text{Im } \epsilon} \frac{d\text{Re } \epsilon}{d\omega} . \quad (4)$$

This formula is independent of geometry and shape of plasmonic materials. For localized surface plasmon (LSP) and propagating surface plasmon-polariton (SPP) modes, the quality factor becomes $Q_{LSP} = -\text{Re } \epsilon / \text{Im } \epsilon$ and $Q_{SPP} = (\text{Re } \epsilon)^2 / \text{Im } \epsilon$, respectively²⁶. Now, the question is: whether these plasmonic quality factors are appropriate for quantifying the efficiency of ENZ materials? In the presence of losses, particularly in the ENZ regime in metallic structures, equation (4) is no longer valid. Even in the lossless regime, $\text{Im } \epsilon \ll \text{Re } \epsilon \ll 1$, the loss function, $L(\omega)$ is expressed as³⁷

$$L(\omega) \approx \frac{1}{\text{Im } \epsilon} \rightarrow \infty , \quad \text{for } \text{Im } \epsilon \rightarrow 0 , \quad (5)$$

exhibiting a diverging singularity at the resonance frequency. This shows that the lossy nature of ENZ materials is independent of the internal dissipation. Even for a very small imaginary part of the permittivity, ENZ materials exhibit significant dissipation, which can be an advantage for perfect-absorption applications. Therefore, alternative definitions for the ENZ quality factors are required.

Some quality factors can be introduced based on the propagation and confinement of the ENZ modes in nanostructures for waveguiding purposes. The ENZ modes have a flat $\omega(k)$ dispersion, leading to an extremely small group velocity according to $v_g = d\omega/dk$. Due to this fact, low velocity propagation is a big issue in ENZ devices although the hybridization with other propagating modes has been proposed to overcome this limit³⁸. To calculate the quality factors for ENZ materials, a single interface of metal-insulator is assumed to support surface plasmon modes. For the sake of simplicity, air ($\epsilon_{air} = 1$) is considered for the insulator part and the propagation length and mode size of ENZ modes are calculated as follows³⁹:

$$L_\omega = \frac{c}{\omega} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{\epsilon_r}}, \quad (6)$$

$$D_\omega = \frac{c}{\omega} \sqrt{-\epsilon_r - 1} + \frac{c}{\omega} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{\epsilon_r^2}} (1 - \ln|\epsilon_r|), \quad (7)$$

where $\epsilon_r = \text{Re } \epsilon$, and c is the speed of light. The propagation length and mode size, L_ω and D_ω are scaled by the ENZ wavelength to make easier comparison over a wide spectrum. As the propagation length and mode size are inversely related, a trade-off between these two parameters should be performed depending on the purpose.

Other quality factors for different applications have been proposed such as the ratio $M = L_\omega/D_\omega$ for plasmonic waveguides⁴⁰ or a figure-of-merit for light modulation applications: $FOM = \frac{\text{Phase Delay}}{\text{Loss}}$, where *Phase delay* and *Loss* are the phase change and intensity attenuation with respect to the incident light. For sensor applications, there are two key parameters which determine the quality factors: the spectral shift $\Delta\lambda$ in response to an applied modification in a material and the full-width-at-half-maximum (FWHM) of the plasmon resonance peak. These enable a figure-of-merit to be proposed as⁴¹

$$FOM = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{FWHM_\lambda}, \quad (8)$$

Notably, ENZ materials typically show a significant enhancement in the quality factor for sensor applications compared to their plasmonic counterparts⁴².

Results

We adopt a convention for considering ENZ materials in which the real permittivity is between $-0.2 < \text{Re } \epsilon < 0.2$. Although in some papers the acceptable range of permittivity for ENZ materials

is $|\text{Re } \epsilon| < 1$, there is no exact definition for the permittivity range⁴³. Narrowing the $|\text{Re } \epsilon|$ range highlights only materials with strongest ENZ feature where the permittivity is in vicinity of zero. On the other hand, the focus on the pronounced ENZ spectrum makes the data presentation more intuitive for the readers. In Figures 1–6 we present materials exhibiting epsilon near zero at specific wavelengths while the imaginary part of permittivity is represented by colours. The real and imaginary parts of permittivity are calculated as $\text{Re } \epsilon = n^2 - k^2$ and $\text{Im } \epsilon = -2nk$, respectively. In these equations, n and k are the refractive index and the extinction coefficient, respectively. The majority of refractive indices and extinction coefficients have been sourced from Palik *et al.*⁴⁴, supplemented by data on additional compounds from other articles⁴⁵. Note that the measured optical parameters might depend on experimental conditions and growth parameters of the material. Therefore, the results have a certain level of uncertainty, which can be checked in Palik *et al.*⁴⁴. We also carried out a survey to compare our results with published experimental results. Furthermore, all raw data and figures with colour bars showing different quality factors are given in the supplementary information.

Notice that for some materials, different ENZ spectra were reported in references indicated by Latin numerals. These discrepancies arise from the growth conditions, thin-film thicknesses, crystalline quality, doping, and many others^{46,47}. Such sensitivity with respect to additional parameters can be employed for controlling optical properties and relevant applications of the materials.

The permittivity changes in a material depend on the ongoing resonances, leading to the occurrence of ENZ properties. Some of the ENZ materials have a characteristic wavelength, such as metallic gallium at 780 nm, due to a sharp transition of the permittivity sign. In contrast, there are materials with a relatively broad ENZ range, such as metallic Au exhibiting a 30 nm bandwidth around 230 nm, with a smooth frequency dependence.

Figure 1. Materials exhibiting an ENZ regime in the extreme ultraviolet range. ENZ regime: $-0.2 < \text{Re } \epsilon < 0.2$. Colour of dots indicates the magnitude of $\text{Im } \epsilon$. For materials such as graphite, Al_2O_3 and GaTe, optical responses along the ordinary and extra-ordinary optical axes are shown with (o) and (eo), respectively. EllX, Y and Z represent the relative directions of the light electric field vectors and crystallographic axes. Furthermore, Latin numerals for some substances are related to different references given in Palik *et al.*⁴⁴.

Figure 2. Materials exhibiting an ENZ regime in the far ultraviolet range. ENZ regime: $-0.2 < \text{Re } \epsilon < 0.2$ and the colour of dots indicates the magnitude of $\text{Im } \epsilon$. For materials such as Te, ZnGaP₂, AgGaSe₂, CuGaS₂, AgGaS₂, CdS and TiO₂ optical responses along the ordinary and extra-ordinary optical axes are shown with (o) and (eo), respectively. Furthermore, Latin numerals for some substances are related to different references given in Palik *et al.*⁴⁴.

Figure 3. Materials exhibiting an ENZ regime in the middle and near ultraviolet range. ENZ regime: $-0.2 < \text{Re } \epsilon < 0.2$ and the colour of dots indicates the magnitude of $\text{Im } \epsilon$. For materials such as Te, ZnGeP₂, TiO₂, CdS, Er, Dy, Se and AgGaSe₂ optical responses along the ordinary and extra-ordinary optical axes are shown with (o) and (eo), respectively; and EllX, Y and Z represent the relative directions of the light electric field vectors and crystallographic axes. The symbols \perp , \parallel c indicate the optical responses for perpendicular and parallel polarizations, respectively. Furthermore, Latin numerals for some substances are related to different references given in Palik *et al.*⁴⁴.

Figure 4. Materials exhibiting an ENZ regime in the visible and near IR range. ENZ regime: $-0.2 < \text{Re } \epsilon < 0.2$ and the colour of dots indicates the magnitude of $\text{Im } \epsilon$. For materials such as Te and Dy, optical responses along the ordinary optical axis are shown with (o) and EIIX, Y and Z represent the relative directions of the light electric field vectors and crystallographic axes. Furthermore, Latin numerals for some substances are related to different references given in Palik *et al.*⁴⁴.

Figure 5. Materials exhibiting an ENZ regime in the Mid-IR range. ENZ regime: $-0.2 < \text{Re } \epsilon < 0.2$ and the colour of dots indicates the magnitude of $\text{Im } \epsilon$. For materials such as CdS, BaTiO₃, Al₂O₃, ZrSiO₄, CuGaS₂, AgGaS₂, CaCO₃, LaTiO₃, SiO₂, TiO₂ and GaTe, optical responses along the ordinary and extra-ordinary optical axes are shown with (o) and (eo), respectively and represent the relative directions of the light electric field vectors and crystallographic axes. Furthermore, Latin numerals for some substances are related to different references given in Palik *et al.*⁴⁴.

Figure 6. Materials exhibiting an ENZ regime in the Far-IR range. ENZ regime: $-0.2 < \text{Re } \epsilon < 0.2$. The colour of dots indicates the magnitude of $\text{Im } \epsilon$. For CaCO₃ optical responses along the extra-ordinary optical axis are shown with (eo). Furthermore, Latin numerals for some substances are related to different references given in Palik *et al.*⁴⁴.

Discussion

Materials with ENZ wavelengths in the *extreme ultraviolet* regime, from ca 40 nm to 100 nm, are presented in Figure 1. Within this range, different materials are featured, spanning from metals (Pt, Fe, Be), semiconductors (GaAs, h-BN) to halide salts, such as NaCl, KCl, thallium chloride (TlCl), and oxide perovskites (LiTaO₃, SrTiO₃, and BaTiO₃). The diversity of materials exhibiting ENZ features in this range is likely attributed to multiple electronic transitions that typically result in significant changes in permittivity values. It is already demonstrated that polyvalent metals, such as In, Sb, Tl and Pb with inter-band electronic transitions show plasmonic behaviours in the

UV range while the plasmonic efficiency of the traditional plasmonic metals, Au and Ag, are not favourable in the same spectral range⁴⁸. Recently, a review on applications of plasmonic materials has drawn attention to possible applications of ENZ materials in the UV range, which show potential for UV detection devices to UV metasurface applications⁴⁹. Although exploiting such plasmonic features at the UV range had been challenging, the progress of nanofabrication techniques has raised the profile of UV plasmonic and ENZ fields within the scientific community. Another interesting point of the data in this range is that different aluminium compounds such as Al_2O_3 , and AlN have similar ENZ features, including ENZ wavelengths and imaginary parts of the permittivity, when compared to metallic Al. This similarity is technically important, particularly between metallic Al and Al_2O_3 , because the oxidation of Aluminium is deleterious for plasmonic efficiency. However, our data demonstrate that oxidation of metals such as Be, Li and Mg changes the ENZ feature. Similarly, it has been reported that oxidation can alter the plasmonic characteristic wavelengths for Mg and Al⁵⁰. Since the size reduction down to the nanoscale increases the chemical activity and facilitates the oxidation process, it is crucial for the ENZ feature to remain unchanged after air exposure.

Materials exhibiting ENZ in the *far ultraviolet*, from 100 to 200 nm, wavelength range are presented in Figure 2. It can be noticed that different compounds made of silver (Ag, AgBr, AgGaS₂, AgGaSe₂), lead (PbTe, PbSe, PbS, PbF₂), indium (In, InSb, InAs) and Ti and TiO₂, all show ENZ features at slightly different wavelengths. In comparison with plasmonic applications, it has been recently demonstrated that the intermetallic compounds from Ag (Au) -p-block metals have higher efficiencies and lower losses in the UV range compared to metallic Ag and Au due to their inter-band transitions in this range⁵¹.

In the literature, metal nitrides are described as promising alternatives to noble metals in plasmonic applications, usually with lower optical losses. For instance, ZrN, HfN and TiN are examples showing plasmonic features in the UV-Vis spectrum²⁷. However, our data show that AlN, TiN and ZrN have ENZ features in the whole UV range as shown in Figures 1 and 2. Especially for TiN, its potential for tuning the ENZ wavelength through changing fabrication processes or temperatures has been demonstrated for both plasmonic and ENZ applications⁵². AlN is also a metal nitride exhibiting a great potential in the ENZ propagation modes at wavelengths below 200 nm. It also showed tremendous field confinement at mid-IR frequencies⁵³.

Materials exhibiting ENZ in the *middle and near ultraviolet*, from 180 to 400 nm wavelength range, are presented in Figure 3. In this range, metallic Au and Ti display a broadband ENZ spectrum, while TiO₂ exhibits extremely narrow band ENZ with high loss. Some alkali metals such as Li, K and Cs also have a narrow ENZ spectrum in this regime, which is related to their plasmon frequencies. However, the high activity of the alkali metals is the major technical obstacle to exploit for ENZ and plasmonic applications.

Another noticeable point from the data in the UV range is a red-shift which has been observed for Hg_{1-x}Cd_xTe by decreasing the mercury concentration, as shown in Figure 3. Such tunability is likely attributed to the variation in bandgap, a characteristic often exploited in infrared detection technology. In the visible and near-infrared spectra, only a few natural materials, mostly metal elements, exhibit an ENZ condition as illustrated in Figure 4. The plasmon frequency of free carriers in the metals has the main role in controlling the permittivity. As indicated in the coloured bars of the figures, the high imaginary part of permittivity leading to optical loss is the primary drawback of metals for ENZ-based applications in that range. It should be noted that very limited applications such as beam steering are proposed for materials with high loss⁵⁴.

Figure 5 presents materials exhibiting an ENZ condition in the mid-IR range from 3 μ m to 50 μ m. Perovskites such as BaTiO₃, LiTiO₃, SrTiO₃ and TbScO₃ show ENZ features between wavelengths of 12-15 μ m. The tunability of ENZ features in these perovskites, whether achieved by controlling growth conditions or through combination in metal-dielectric hybrid structures, is recognized as a distinct advantage for the metamaterial technology⁵⁵. Although in this paper we focus only on inorganic ENZ materials, it is worth noting that organic-inorganic perovskite compounds were recently proposed to manipulate the dielectric permittivity to reach the ENZ regime⁵⁶.

Alkali metal fluorides such as LiF, NaF, CaF₂, MgF₂, BaF₂ and SrF₂, exhibit ENZ features in the MIR range. However, there are currently no experimental reports exploiting their potentials for metamaterial applications.

In the far-IR range, spanning from 50 μ m to 100 μ m, again the number of materials exhibiting ENZ features decreases, as shown in Figure 6. The main reason for reducing the number of ENZ materials is likely attributed to overall increases in permittivity as a result of the strong polar ionic contributions. Particularly in this range, THz absorption due to phonon resonances may cause a

transient reduction in the permittivity depending on the absorption strength. In this regard, alkali halide salts such as KCl, KBr, KI, RbBr and RbI have ENZ wavelengths in the far infrared (FIR) frequencies due to phonon dispersion. These materials are potentially promising candidates for THz applications. Yet, care should be taken that the ENZ spectral range is sufficiently far from phonon resonances, because a very sharp transition in permittivity occurs around the phonon resonance. This drastic transition can potentially change the sign of permittivity and introduce ENZ features.

By comparing the imaginary parts of the permittivities in Figures 1–6, we found no direct relation between losses and the spectral range. While the highest values are observed in the Near-IR range, other spectral regions contain materials with very low loss. For instance, Al in the extreme UV, Mg in the far UV, K and Cs in the middle and near UV, ZrSiO₄ and hBN in the mid-IR, and NaNO₃ in the Far-IR exhibit some of the lowest losses. These characteristics make them promising candidates for ENZ waveguide applications, where loss mitigation remains a major challenge¹⁶.

Semiconductors exhibit ENZ features in different spectra such as UV, mid and far IR. The low inter-band losses of semiconductors, especially III-V semiconductors is of great advantage compared to metal counterparts for the Vis and NIR range²⁷. Moreover, changing carrier concentration through doping in semiconductors can tune the Drude contributions in ϵ values and consequently change the ENZ wavelength. Interestingly, we have found ENZ in the UV spectrum, for GaAs, InSb, InAs and ZnTe likely stems from different electronic transitions in the high energy ranges. However, possible applications of this feature have yet to be explored.

One of the most interesting details which has been revealed by our data is the anisotropic characteristic of the ENZ spectrum, where the ENZ feature exists for only one of the crystal orientations/optical axis. For example, GaTe, Al₂O₃ in the extreme UV spectrum, Te(p) and Te(n), CuGaS₂(o and eo), ZnGaP₂ (o and eo), Se (o and e), ZnGeP₂, Dy, Er, CdS(eo), CaCo₃, ZrSiO₄, AgGaS₂, AgGaSe₂, BaTiO₃, LiTaO₃, SiO₂. Such anisotropy can appear due to different reasons. For example, in AgGaS, anisotropic electron distribution among Ag, Ga and S has the major contribution⁵⁷, whereas in BaTiO₃, the presence of a soft mode in its tetragonal crystal structure is responsible for anisotropy⁵⁸. This potentially enables the propagation of anisotropic surface waves and arbitrary control of electromagnetic flux by making inhomogeneous anisotropic

media⁵⁹. Such an intrinsic anisotropy in natural materials gives them a remarkable advantage over nanoengineered structures with their costly processing and chemical degradation.

ENZ wavelength modulation is also possible by external manipulation such as controlling charge concentration by doping routes⁶⁰, applying external electric fields⁶¹, control temperature⁶² and post-thermal treatment.

To demonstrate the functionality of the presented ENZ materials, their quality factors are calculated at ENZ wavelengths. The quality factors are the normalized propagation length factor ($Q_{Pr} = \frac{L\omega}{\lambda_{ENZ}}$), normalized ENZ mode size ($Q_{con} = \frac{D\omega}{\lambda_{ENZ}}$) and a parameter similar to the plasmonic quality factor ($Q = \frac{Re \epsilon}{Im \epsilon}$) in this study. The optimal materials for each application are presented in Figures 7 to 9 across a broad wavelength range. Figure 7 indicates that Rh, metallic Al, Mg and K exhibit the highest values of Q throughout the entire UV range. Previous studies have demonstrated that Al, Mg, Ag, Au and Cu possess the highest plasmonic quality factors, particularly in the UV and visible spectral ranges⁵⁰. These similarities arise from the use of similar formulae, although Q is calculated at $Re \epsilon \approx 0$ for ENZ applications and $Re \epsilon \approx -2$ for plasmonic applications.

Figure 7. ENZ materials with the highest plasmon-based quality factor (Q) for $Re \epsilon \approx 0$.

Figure 8. ENZ materials enabling propagation of the highest number of wavelengths.

The normalized propagation length of ENZ mode is considered as the ratio of the propagation length to the exciting ENZ wavelength. In Figure 8, materials with the highest Q_{Pr} are presented for each wavelength range. For example, gallium at 80K is the most supportive material for ENZ mode propagation with $Q_{Pr} \approx 17$. Although the plasmonic properties of gallium particles and their tunability with particle size have been previously demonstrated⁶³, there is a lack of reports regarding their capability to support ENZ mode propagation. As will be shown later, despite exhibiting a high quality factor and extended propagation length, their ability to squeeze electromagnetic fields remains limited. The data reveals that high Q_{Pr} values are achievable in the visible range, whereas below 200 nm, the mid-IR and far-IR ranges the possibilities for ENZ mode propagation are much reduced. Therefore, ENZ mode propagation in those ranges needs structural engineering to overcome the inherent weakness of these materials.

Figure 9. ENZ materials with the most efficient confinement factors.

In Figure 9, we have summarized the ENZ materials with highest capabilities of EM field confinement for all wavelength ranges. Lower Q_{con} values are more favourable since they indicate that the material is capable of EM field squeezing. Therefore, Al₂O₃ is the most capable natural material for field confinement in the near IR range and along its extraordinary optical direction. Titanium also exhibits high confinement factor but for a different wavelength range (NIR). A detailed report on experimental realization of ENZ materials, including metals, semi-metals, interbands and phononic materials can be seen in Kinsey *et al.*⁶⁴. However, there are still no experimental demonstrations for the highlighted key materials listed in this paper, despite their promising potential for ENZ-based applications.

Conclusion

We have presented a comprehensive set of materials with permittivity around zero, along with application-specific quality factors, highlighting the wide range of potential applications for Epsilon Near Zero (ENZ) media. Interestingly, we have identified a large number of materials exhibiting ENZ features at less than 400 nm where, until now, there has been relatively little effort dedicated to finding niche applications in the UV spectrum. According to our data, gallium emerges as the most effective natural material for the ENZ mode propagation; however, the relative EM field confinement is approximately 1.65, indicating that it is a ‘leaky’ medium for storing EM energy. In terms of EM field storage, Al₂O₃ exhibits the highest quality factor in the near-IR. In general,

natural ENZ materials can have significant advantages over artificial nanoengineered structures with their costly processing and chemical degradation.

Supporting Information

All figures showing ENZ materials and corresponding quality factors such as the normalized propagation length, the normalized ENZ mode sizes and plasmon-based quality factor are given in supporting information. Additionally, all related raw data is given in a separate Excel file.

Acknowledgment

The authors thank ENSEMBLE3 Project (MAB/2020/14) which is carried out within the International Research Agendas Programme (IRAP) of the Foundation for Polish Science co-financed by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund and Teaming Horizon 2020 programme (GA. No. 857543) of the European Commission and the project of the Minister of Science and Higher Education "Support for the activities of Centers of Excellence established in Poland under the Horizon 2020 program" under contract No. MEiN/2023/DIR/3797. K.Y.B. acknowledges support from Marie Skłodowska-Curie COFUND Programme of the European Commission (project HORIZON- MSCA-2022-COFUND-101126600-SmartBRAIN3).

Funding Sources

International Research Agendas Programme (IRAP) of the Foundation for Polish Science co-financed by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund (MAB/2020/14), Teaming Horizon 2020 programme of the European Commission (GA. No. 857543), Minister of Science and Higher Education "Support for the activities of Centers of Excellence established in Poland under the Horizon 2020 program" (MEiN/2023/DIR/3797), Marie Skłodowska-Curie COFUND Programme of the European Commission (HORIZON- MSCA-2022-COFUND-101126600-SmartBRAIN3).

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Compendium of Natural Epsilon-Near-Zero Materials

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Figure description: The main scope of this paper is presenting list of natural materials with epsilon-near-zero behaviour. These materials can be categorized by semiconductors, Perovskites, metals, semi-metals and insulators. Based on the optical properties of these materials in the ENZ spectrum, we present the application-based quality factors quantifying the performance of ENZ materials for EM field enhancement, ENZ mode propagation and plasmonic applications. Additionally, real and imaginary part of permittivity of TiN is presented as an example and an ENZ region which is $|Re(\epsilon)| < 0.2$.